

Content Marketing And Sales Performance Of Real Estate Firms In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effect of content marketing on sale performance of real estate firms in Anambra State of Nigeria. This study became necessary following the low patronage been witnessed by real estate firms and their agents due to economic downturn. The study specifically sought to ascertain how content marketing can be used to enhance the sales performance of real estate firms. Related conceptual, theoretical and empirical literatures were reviewed. Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology was adopted as the theoretical framework. The study adopted descriptive research design and a total of 44 real estate firms in the state were studied. A sample of 385 respondents was used and questionnaire served as the instrument of data collection. Descriptive statistics and regression technique was employed in analyzing the data. The result indicates that content marketing platform has a significant effect on sales performance of real estate firms in Anambra State. The study recommends that real estate firms should invest more on content marketing since it enhanced the sales performance of the real estate firms. Also, content marketing should be design in such a way that it creates a healthy interaction and emotional involvement with the existing and prospective customers.

Keywords: Contents Marketing Sales Performance, Real Estate

INTRODUCTION

The role of content marketing in real estate has grown profoundly over the past few years. In an industry that once used print media as its primary form of delivering the marketing message, there is now an urgent need to have transitioned to the internet in order to reach today's homebuyer. An online presence is a vital component of a real estate professional's marketing strategy. Because today's consumers want accurate information quickly and conveniently, real estate professionals must harness the features and capabilities of content marketing to meet these ever-increasing needs. Content marketing platform is a marketing technique which involves creating and spreading contents valuable from the point of view of recipients of the content, aimed at drawing attention and thus engaging a community gathered around a particular target group. Content are what users wanted to read, learn about, watch or experience. Content marketing is a form of marketing focused on creating, publishing, and distributing content for a targeted audience online (Lieb, 2020).

Sales performance on the other hand is a set of operational and analytical functions that automate and unite back-office operational sales processes and is implemented to improve operational efficiency and effectiveness. Sales performance refers to how effectively the sales team performs within a specific period of time. Evaluating sales performance is one of the most common ways to track and manage sales representatives work from the beginning and beyond (Kotler & Armstrong, 2022). This is majorly because

the people now have improved online presence and engagements, which affects their attention to offline activities, to a reasonable extent. Sales performance can be measured by sales volume, sales revenue, market share, sales turnover, sales growth and profit after sales of real estate firms. In most companies, the sales function is performed by sales people (Kotane, Znotina & Hushko, 2019).

In a bid to address the problem of not having a recognized open market for real estate as well as other problems that also affect the sales performance of real estate firms in Nigeria; some real estate owners and managers have tried different traditional and conventional means of capturing the attention of their customers/real estate buyers. They have resorted to advertising, word of mouth marketing, personal selling, sales promotional activities and other traditional offline strategies to market real estate products (Frank, 2021) but they are still experiencing intense competition, low sales volume, low sales revenue, low market share, low sales turnover, low sales growth and profit after sales is still low (Etim, Edim, Arikpo & Okeowo, 2021; Etuk, Udo & Udowong, 2021). Therefore, the adoption and use of online marketing particularly content marketing is the key and the solution needed for effective and efficient sales performance of real estate firms in Nigeria. The dawn of content marketing as a new age competitive strategy which is an offshoot of technology is the key especially when engaging in different aspects of businesses. Real estate is one of such businesses that yield greater output as a result of the use of online marketing platforms (Jejelola & Ogungbe 2020). Importantly, online marketing platforms enable the real estate customers/buyers get access to available real estate properties and gain online presence more conveniently which in return boost the performance of real estate firms.

The absence of standard formal market or recognized open markets for real estate business in Nigeria is the motivation that prompted this study (Etim et al, 2021). The problem of no formal estate market coupled with other problems such as high transaction costs for real estate products, difficulty to sell real estate property, low liquidity, low sales turnover, intense competition as well as high level of risks are the issues of great concern which have brought this topic to limelight (Etuk et al, 2021; Emoh, 2021). Besides, other problems which real estate firms are facing include high operational costs, limited identification and access to the buyers, poor track for potential buyers of real estate and delay in business transaction. Regrettably, the market share of real estate business in Nigeria is still very low (Kakulu, 2018). Unfortunately, many real estate firms in Nigeria seem not to have or appeared not to have started using online marketing strategies particularly content marketing (Abiodun & Kolade, 2020). Indisputably, all these problems affect the sales performance of real estate firms in Nigeria. Therefore the main problem of this study is lack of formal market for real estate in Nigeria (Etim et al, 2021).

Precisely, in Anambra State, not all real estate firms know about content marketing. Even those that have known and use it do not know the extent to which it affects the sales performance of real estate. Based on the fact that real estate business cannot flourish in the face of the challenging problems (Babatunde, 2016) coupled with the need to improve their sales performance; many researchers have conduct many empirical studies on the subject matter in efforts to address the problems and also to fill the research gap. Unfortunately, their empirical findings yielded conflicting results. Therefore these inconsistencies in the findings by different researchers suggest that more empirical studies like the present study on the effect of content marketing on sales performance are needed since the issue of conflicting findings has not been resolved. Hence, this study sought to investigate the effect of content marketing on sale performance of real estate firms in Anambra State of Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Content Marketing Platform

Content marketing is a marketing technique which involves creating and spreading contents valuable from the point of view of recipients of the content, aimed at drawing attention and thus engaging a community gathered around a particular target group (Dave, 2016). Content is what user wants to read, learn about, watch or experience. From the perspective of business, content is important information presented on a website, in an application or by means of other available channels of digital presentation, which have the mission of communicating. Content marketing refers to the creation and sharing of

valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and retain a target audience and ultimately drive profitable customer action (Chauhan & Pillai, 2023). The goal of content marketing is to educate and engage potential customers in order to build trust and loyalty, and eventually turn them into customers. This can be achieved through various channels such as blogs, social media, email marketing, videos, podcasts, and more. Effective content marketing requires a strategic approach and a commitment to providing valuable information to the target audience on a consistent basis.

The term content marketing refers to a method of marketing that includes creating and sharing online content that doesn't just promote a brand, but rather is designed to encourage its audience to visit a brand's website. Brand awareness is increased by using storytelling and sharing information. The goal is to get the readers to take a step toward becoming a customer, such as requesting more information, signing up, or making a purchase. Generally, content marketing is about offering benefits to the consumer rather than only marketing a brand (Ahmad et al., 2016). Content marketing can include blog posts, white papers, digital books, podcasts, digital videos, etc. With content marketing, you can build a sustainable relationship with your clients that can lead to numerous sales over time. Keyes (2016) view content marketing is usually focuses on intranet-based or internet-based corporate content, including data and knowledge bases. Pulizzi and Barret (2019) defined content marketing is a marketing technique of creating and distributing relevant and valuable content to attract, acquire, and engage a clearly defined and understood target audience with the objective of driving profitable customer action. Content marketing is very important as opposed to renting media. It's marketing process to attract and retain customers by consistently creating and curating content in order to change or enhance sales performance of real estate (Halvorson 2019).

Content marketing is a strategic marketing approach that focuses on creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and retain a clearly defined audience, and ultimately, drive profitable customer action (Kapur & Chaturvedi, 2021). It's about creating content that people want and need, and sharing it in a way that is engaging, informative and persuasive. Content marketing is a form of marketing focused on creating, publishing, and distributing content for a targeted audience online (Lieb, 2019). It is often used by businesses in order to achieve the following goals: attract attention and generate leads, expand their customer base, generate or increase online sales, increase brand awareness or credibility, and engage an online community of users. Content marketing attracts new customers by creating and sharing valuable free content. It helps companies create sustainable brand loyalty, provides valuable information to consumers, and creates a willingness to purchase products from the company in the future (Lieb, 2019). Content marketing starts with identifying the customer's needs. After that the information can be presented in a variety of formats, including news, video, white papers, e-books, infographics, email newsletters, case studies, podcasts, how-to guides, question and answer articles, photos, blogs, Content marketing requires continuous delivery of large amounts of content, preferably within a content marketing strategy (Pulizzi & Barrett, 2018).

Nowadays content marketing is not just a desirable thing, it's a must-have. Moreover, it is necessary to create up-to-date content. Naturally, this cannot be regular content, but it has to be reliable, high-quality content. On top of that it has to be valuable enough to provide the recipient with benefits that can satisfy his needs and expectations in course of interaction. An important aspect of content marketing is also defining the target group, which is supposed to receive the content of the message. This in turn creates the necessity to create and later distribute such information that will introduce the recipient into the brand, product or service area, which is the subject of the message. The strategy of customer engagement marketing is nothing new. However, its relentless development and the growing importance of Internet platforms 2.0 mean that the strategy has reached the top of the list of most popular strategies in the branch.

Customer engagement marketing is nothing else but a transition from one direction campaigns (relations) to a strategy based on a dialogue with the client. As opposed to traditional and in practice, often invasive strategies, which corner the recipient, customer engagement marketing defines, identifies real, specific needs of customers. By assumption it also encourages the consumer to interaction, to real, active

participation in the development of its brand, product or service. As Rebecca Lieb writes in her book titled "Content Marketing" the term appeared in 2019. By that moment nobody had heard of or used this term. Earlier, the branch used numerous terms in order to characterize actions surrounding brand creation, such as: custom publishing, custom media, customer media, customer publishing, member media, private media, branded content, corporate media, corporate publishing, corporate journalism or branded media. Content marketing in its assumptions isn't based solely on persuasive actions targeted at a chosen group of recipients and its exceptional character to a large extent is mostly about providing the recipient with particular arguments and possibilities of benefits (Vimerean, 2017).

Sales Performance

Sales performance is the effectiveness of the sales team, both individually and as a whole, in selling activities; the ability to achieve sales goals. Sales performance can be measured in a variety of ways depending on the sales role and sales environment, such as sales revenue, sales turnover, sales volume, sales growth, market share, customers retention rate, profits after sales or number of net new accounts. Sales performance is how effective your sales team members are at hitting their goals. Sales revenue is one way to measure performance, but there are many other metrics, such as time spent per customer or the amount of repeat business they generate.

The sales performance is based on efficiency and effectiveness, with efficiency fitting the real estate functions and environment and costing considerably less than the input per unit cost per output. The real estate ability to meet its customer, such as employees, managers, and stakeholder groups; the company's ability to achieve its current objectives; and the organization's ability to adapt continuously to online marketing platform Kaario et al. (2023) noted that sales performance represents the next generation of best practices for sales. It establishes a strong foundation for improving sales execution. Sales performance refers to how effectively your sales team performs within a specific period of time. Implementing sales performance is one of the most common ways to track and manage sales reps' work from the beginning and beyond. Standardized measures, values and processes also make it easier to develop best practice methods and evaluate key steps in the sales process (Kaario et al., 2023).

Storbacka et al. (2019) describe sales performance as the process of coordinating and improving the sales department of a company. In this management method, supervisors track the activities and productivity rates of employees to guide and support them in improving in their roles. Typically, sales performance aims to provide helpful resources for employees, increase sales rates and raise profits. This management style can help salespeople with planning objectives, developing skills and fulfilling customer expectations. Sales control (sales performance measurement) is most often divided in to two separate approaches, outcome and behavior measurements, as described by Küster & Canales (2020). They describe the difference between the two as behavior measurement being the more subjective, with reporting based on manager's perception of the sales person performance while, outcome based measurements allow for measurements that are more objective. Which approach a company decides to go with often depends on what information is easier for the company to access. Based on their research, they also note that the chosen method of sales control has a large impact on the compensation system (bonus) as well as organizational effectiveness. They concluded that for best results, a combination of outcome and behavioral measures should be utilized.

Kaario et al. (2023) found that if a sales person is able to identify an opportunity for customer process innovation and is also able to deliver a solution capable of creating the expected value, then the role of service/solutions provider shifts to that of a trusted partner. Because sales people are in daily contact with customers and know what they value, it is important that they are included in the development of the sales process and the evaluation tools used to measure the delivery of Value Sales. Kaario et al. (2003) state that value sales demand a better understanding of solutions and applications as well as team-effort and the need to measure not only financial results but also identifying HR strategies and adapting to the new sales structure. The skills identified by them required by a sales-person to succeed in a value selling environment are not only personal selling skills, but also the skill to sell according to the company "way". Sales people need to take in account customer retention, knowledge of customer business logic ("how")

and have the ability to provide the customer with input for development of the customers' operations. Based on their analysis of the available literature on sales performance measurement Zal-locco et al. (2019) found that for the measurement points to have meaning for sales managers and salespersons should be involved in the development process. They found that this is most often not the case, and they found that there was a large gap between the company strategy and the salesperson understanding of the measurement points Sales performance management is important because it helps a business succeed, improve and grow. Putting effort into sales performance management system also helps support the work and well-being of employees (Kaario et al., 2023).

Content Marketing and Sales Performance

In recent years both practitioners and academics have shown an increasing interest in content marketing and how it impact business success. However , the literature remain very poor in developing nations as regard its effectiveness and impact on sales performance of real estate . Based on above observation, and in attempting to fill the gap, arose the need for this study, bearing in mind that content marketing is becoming one of the hottest academic and practical topics in the business field across the world. Hence, the major objective of this research is to provide knowledge regarding whether content marketing as marketing strategy practices is being practiced by companies in Nigeria, and if yes , to investigate if it is beneficial to business success and sales performance of real estate. Content marketing is not by any means a new phenomenon. It has as a marketing strategy undergone a deep evolution and has occupied the centre stage of practice of marketing strategy across the world. It is becoming one of the hottest academic and practical topics in the business field. In recent years, studies on content marketing have significantly increased and different definitions of content marketing have been suggested by different authors without reaching a clear and unique definition.

Furthermore, content strategy is the practice of planning for the creation, delivery, and governance of useful, usable content (Handley & Chapman, 2019). Content marketing is anything an individual or an organization creates and/or shares to tell their story. Gunelius (2018) view content marketing as the process of indirectly and directly promoting a business or brand through value-added text, video, or audio content both online and offline. It can come in long-form (such as blogs, articles, e-books, and so on), short - form (such as Twitter updates, Facebook updates, images, and so on), or conversational - form (for example, sharing great content via Twitter or participating in an active discussion via blog comments or through an online forum.

Lieb (2018) content marketing, in other words, is nothing new. Companies having been creating and distributing content for many years, both to attract new business and retain existing customers. However, here's the point of differentiation from more traditional forms of marketing and advertising: using selling. It isn't advertising. It isn't push marketing, in which messages are sprayed out at groups of consumers. Rather it is a pull strategy attraction. It's being there when consumers need you and seek you out with relevant, educational, helpful, compelling, engaging, and sometimes entertaining information. Slater (2014) Content marketing is a dynamic way to get customers. It is the process of sharing expertise and knowledge online to attract potential customers and establish a relationship with them. In addition, content marketers have to be focused on creating, publishing, and sharing suitable content.

However, many content marketers often overlook a readily available source of content articles, blog posts, videos, images, and other assets that were created years before yet still have the potential to draw new customers; and Ramos (2014) content marketing is a marketing techniques that uses high-quality, relevant content to educate, engage, and acquire your target customer. Furthermore, content marketing is not just creating content for the sake of producing content; your objective is always sales. The true potential of content marketing lies in its ability to provide a conversion path for your leads to follow on their own schedule and at their convenience.

Rancati (2014) also posited the three pillars that characterize content marketing as contents; customers engagement and goals. With reference to the first pillar, content marketing is viewed as means to produce quality content, unique, significant, valuable, dynamic and more relevant content than that of competitors. It is also posit that the content must: be able to generate interest, must be involving, but also informing

and educating the customer; and thus, express all those values that identify the firm in terms of uniqueness, consistency, quality and relevance. It must be pro-active, and able to evolve over time (Lieb, 2019). Likewise extant literature also has it that, content marketing helps meet consumer goals and organizational goals (Jefferson & Tanton, 2023).

According to extant literature, content marketing helps meet consumer goals by building a supporting, loyal, trusting relationships between brands and consumers; help dominates consumers' online experiences by helping to create the engaging experiences that customers seek and helps develop deeper connections between brands and consumers ; directing a leading driver of brand engagement on Pay per click and motivates consumers to take action ; and help in targeting younger demographics (Jefferson & Tanton, 2023; Weeks & Holbert, 2023). Content marketing impacts organizational goals. Companies that document a strategic content marketing program can have more effective lead generation. Content marketing is leading the pack both in lead generation and in turning those leads into customers. And those organizations demonstrating an ongoing commitment to content marketing create team efficiencies by building staffing infrastructure, establishing quality standards, and creating processes for producing content more efficiently and effectively. The flexibility afforded by content marketing techniques enables businesses to realize measurable results (Rowley 2018).

Content marketing has become a buzzword for corporate marketers as more and more companies or brands are planning to be the publisher of their own content, delivered through a variety of new media channels such as Facebook, Twitter, and Youtube. Instead of advertising, the shift is towards publishing. Companies of all types and sizes flood the market with articles, white papers, videos, podcasts, Facebook posts, and tweets. Common types of content employed in a content marketing strategy include: blog posts or articles white papers, eBooks, and reports podcasts email newsletter or nurturing campaigns videos thought leadership or POVs Info graphics. Benchmark Report (2014) posit that the future of content marketing looks bright , and that content marketing has helped growth of industry in terms of adoption, usage, and availability of resources. Overall, industry projections indicate strong growth in content marketing budgets, and that this has led tremendously to business success. Hence, organizations typically use content marketing to build an audience and to achieve at least one of these profitable results: increased revenue, lower costs, or better customers and among others (Campbel Macdonald, 2015).

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on unified theory of acceptance and use of technology by Venkatesh et al. (2003). The theory states that the actual use of technology like online marketing platform is determined by behavioural intention of the users. According to this theory, the perceived likelihood of adopting the technology like online marketing is dependent on the direct effect of four key constructs, namely performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social Effect, and facilitating conditions. The effect of predictors is moderated by age, gender, experience and voluntariness of use of the online users (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The original UTAUT framework was developed to explain and predict the acceptance of technology in an organizational context, although, later it was tested in non-organizational settings too. Over the years, UTAUT showed wide application, which enhanced the generalisability of the theory. Given the variance of information communication technologies and the advances in the sector, a number of scholars extended UTAUT to adapt it to the context or improve its predictive power (Venkatesh, Thong & Xu, 2022).

The adaptations of the model were underpinned by four main approaches, reflecting; the modification of the model to different contexts, the alterations of the endogenous variables, the addition of attitudinal antecedents, and the examination of various moderating variables. The first stream of research extended the model to apply it to new technologies (enterprise systems, real estate), focus on new user segments of Pay-per-click marketing, e-mail marketing, search engine marketing, mobile marketing, affiliate marketing, and content marketing and examine it in new geographical and cultural settings (India, China) (Gupta, Dasgupta & Gupta, 2023). For instance, the model was extended by a set of web-specific

constructs, including trust and personal web innovativeness to explore how well it predicts the use of web tools (Casey & Wilson-Evered, 2022).

Venkatesh et al. proposed an extension of UTAUT, named UTAUT2 (Venkatesh, Thong & Xu, 2022). The model set out to address two main objectives. First, compared to all prior attempts to extend the model, UTAUT was not designed to have a specific focus (new technology, geographical location). Instead, the goal of the theory was to represent an overarching framework for examining technology acceptance. The extension was designed to give a higher precision in explaining user of online marketing platform (Venkatesh, Thong & Xu, 2022; Alvensson & Kärreman, 2007). The second objective was to propose a behavioural model of consumer technology acceptance, in contrast to UTAUT, which was developed to examine technology in organizational sales performance settings. To fulfil the objective, Venkatesh et al. planned to extend the UTAUT model with new constructs, tackling behavioural and attitudinal determinants of the utilization of technology effect on online marketing platform context (Venkatesh, Thong & Xu, 2022).

Importantly, the authors developed UTAUT by introducing three new constructs and altering some relationships between online marketing platform and performance in the original model to adapt it to sales performance technology use context. Such an approach offered a new theoretically justified mechanism for predicting technology acceptance, which was encouraged and endorsed by prior research (Venkatesh, Davis & Morris, 2007). In addition to advancing the technology acceptance literature (Venkatesh, Thong & Xu, 2022), UTAUT aimed to achieve wider generalisability by addressing the private user segment. UTAUT postulates that the use of technology by individuals is underpinned by the effect of the three additional constructs, namely, hedonic motive, cost/perceived value and habit, moderated by age, gender and experience. Hedonic motivation is defined "as the fun or pleasure derived from using technology, and it has been shown to play an important role in determining technology acceptance and use" (Venkatesh, Thong & Xu, 2022).

UTAUT have a number of applications in practice by real estate firms. UTAUT can be used to examine the anticipated acceptance rate of real estate products so as to ensure sufficient sales performance to satisfy the consumers' demand. Evidence that the model provides can be used by real estate firms to design more online marketing platform particularly content marketing. Also, UTAUT underscores the role of online marketing Effect and facilitating conditions, thus highlighting the importance of contextual analysis in strategies for technology implementation to online marketing platform (Venkatesh, Thong & Xu, 2022). The application of UTAUT enables online marketing vendors to measure how the trade-off their product by utilization of their technology. Companies have the opportunity to reconsider cost-structures to adjust the pricing policy to the relative value attached to the product, because the benefits that users get from the purchase of technology may not justify the price that they pay.

Empirical Studies

Udegbe, (2017) investigates the impact of content marketing as strategies for business success in some Nigerian companies. A survey research design was adopted and research was based on convenience sampling method. Copies of questionnaire were administered to 700 respondents from selected staff of service and manufacturing companies in Nigeria and 584 useable questionnaires were returned (83.43%). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, percentages and t-test analysis. Validity and reliability test indicate that all variables were valid and reliable. Based on the data analysis, the findings revealed that majority of the respondents scored the issues raised in the questionnaire positively, but at different varied levels. However, it is found that content marketing as strategies for business success, is practiced to a reasonable extent, and vigorously integrated into the activities of the surveyed companies in Nigeria because of its benefits. Feedback from the research will assist to expand knowledge as to the usefulness of content marketing.

Eshiett, Eshiett and Uwhubetine (2022) examined the effect of content marketing in directing traffic to a particular content owner through an increased level of customer loyalty. The study defines and appraises the concept of digital content marketing and the effect of engaging marketing content on customer loyalty.

The respondents for this study were postgraduate students of Ahmadu Bello University, Nigeria. The study designed and administered some Content marketing-related questions that could induce customer loyalty to respondents. The data obtained from the study were analyzed using the Pearson Correlation Coefficient technique; the study revealed that the accomplishment of unambiguous and dependable content by business concerns could increase the delight of organizational customers. The analysis of data revealed that there is a link between digital content marketing and customer loyalty in Nigerian Universities.

Nwogu and Ifeakandu (2021) examined which real estate firms in Nigeria make use of online marketing in the disposal of real estate and categories of online marketing platforms used by real estate firms in Nigeria. The study population is real estate property disposal. Sample size is 186 while statistical tool used was One-sample T-Test. The result showed that real estate firms in Nigeria make use of online marketing in the disposal of real estate. The finding confirmed the acceptance of facebook, twitter, whatsapp and Instagram as categories of online marketing platforms used by the Real Estate firms in Nigeria.

Nganga (2022) investigated the impact of digital marketing on performance of small and medium enterprises in Nairobi Central Business District, Kenya. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain the impact of social media marketing, search engine marketing and content marketing on performance of small and medium enterprises. The research design used in the study was descriptive. The population of the study comprised 2100 principle managers of small and medium enterprises operating in the Nairobi CBD and 393 respondents were sampled for the study. Multiple regression and correlation analyses were employed in analyzing the data. The study found that social media marketing, search engine marketing and content marketing have significant impact on performance of small and medium enterprises.

Oyedele, Oworu and Adbulganiyu (2020) carried out a study on online marketing and the performance of small-scale enterprises in Nigeria with particular reference to SMEs in Ikeja, Lagos State. The study adopted survey research design and a total of 221 SMEs were studied. Questionnaire was employed as the instrument of data collection. ANOVA, the correlation, and the regression were employed in analyzing the data. The study found that the online marketing affected the performance of SME positively which has allowed youths to be self-employed and created economic growth and regional development. The study recommends that businesses should develop plans and create a budget for exploiting digital marketing tools and applications to enjoy its superior benefits over traditional marketing; reach target customers better, promote products and services via e-mails, display advertisements, mobile apps, search engine optimization and search engine marketing & online contents and boost their market share; effectively mitigating increasing competition and maximize SMEs potential access to new markets.

Teuta (2023) investigated the impact of digital marketing on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in North Macedonia. The study specifically examined the impact of digital marketing on sales revenue, customer acquisition, brand awareness and performance. Survey using stratified random sampling was conducted, with 165 companies from different areas in North Macedonia randomly selected for the study. The study adopted survey research design. The findings of this study reveal that SMEs in North Macedonia are increasingly utilizing digital marketing strategies, with social media marketing and email marketing being the most used channels. Moreover, digital marketing is found to have a significant positive impact on SME performance, particularly in terms of increasing sales revenue and enhancing customer engagement.

Hindu (2021) carried out a study on digital marketing and business performance in the medium-scale enterprises in Abuja. The study specifically examined the effect of e-mail marketing and social media marketing on performance of SMEs in Abuja. The study adopted survey research design and a total of sixty-three (63) owners/managers of medium-sized businesses in Abuja were sampled for the study. Pearson correlation and regression analysis were employed in analyzing the data. The results indicates that social media marketing and e-mail marketing has significant positive influence on SMEs performance in Abuja.

Eke (2022) investigated the influence of online marketing on marketing performance of small and medium scale businesses in Akwa Ibom State Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design and the sample consisted of 366 SMEs operators across the three senatorial districts in Akwa Ibom State. Data collected with the use of structured questionnaire were formulated tested and analyzed using the simple linear regression. The study found that there is significant relationship between online marketing (proxied by e-mail marketing and search engine marketing) and marketing performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Akwa Ibom State. The study concluded that e-mail marketing and search engine marketing does enhance marketing performance of micro, small and medium scale enterprises in Akwa Ibom State. Njelita, Onyeagwara and Ekwunife (2023) investigated the impact of online marketing on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Anambra State. The study specifically focused on the influence of social media marketing on customer satisfaction/loyalty and market share. The study adopted survey design and a total of 50,213 employees and operators from 2,233 registered SMEs in Anambra State were sampled for the study. The Alien Taro Yamane (1967) was employed to arrive at a sample size of 397. Simple percentages and simple regression analysis were employed in analyzing the data. The revealed that social media marketing significantly influences customer satisfaction/loyalty and market share.

The empirical literature reviewed revealed conflicting findings on the effect of content marketing on sales performance. Similarly, majority of the scholarly work reviewed particularly were concentrated on other sector without giving real estate sector adequate coverage, hence a big knowledge gap. There is also paucity of recent work that covered real estate sector in Anambra State. Despite the previous extensive research work, there is evident gap in knowledge in terms of the area (Anambra State) covered in this study.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive research design. This study is carried out in Anambra State using Awka, Onitsha, Nnewi, Ekwulobia, and Obosi areas as point of reference. Anambra State is a state in southeastern part of Nigeria. The target population of study comprises 1994 employees of 44 real estate firms in the selected areas. Sample size of 385 was determined using the statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall (1973). The data sourced through structured questionnaire were presented and analyzed using quantitative data analysis methods. Tables of frequency and percentage were used. Data from the field survey were coded and entered into the computer using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS Version 25) for analysis. The study employed a Simple Regression Analysis (SRA) method to ascertain the effect of content marketing on sales performance of real estate firms in Anambra State.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

In this section, the demographic features of the respondents such as gender, marital status, age bracket, and highest educational qualification level are presented and analyzed. A total of three hundred and fifty four respondents were sampled and the results are presented in the Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Features of the Respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender		
Male	203	57.3
Female	151	42.7
Marital Status		
Single	130	36.7
Married	180	50.9
Others	44	12.4
Age Range		
18-30 years	130	36.7
31- 40years	120	33.9
41- 50years	70	19.7
Above 50 years	34	9.7
Highest Education Level		
O' Level	20	5.7
OND/NCE	136	38.4
BSc./HND	153	43.2
MSc./MBA/MPhil	40	11.3
Ph.D/Others	15	4.2
Total	354	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents used in field survey. Based on the field survey finding on gender, a higher proportion of the respondents (57.3%) are male while 42.7% of the respondents are female. This implies that both males and females use online marketing platforms although males participate more than females. Also, Table 1 shows that 130 (36.7%) of the respondents are single, 180 (50.9%) are married. while the remaining 44 (12.4%) of the respondents are either divorced or separated. Furthermore, Table 1 depicts the age bracket of the respondents. The distribution shows that 36.7% of the respondents are between the age brackets of 18 to 30 years while 120 respondents representing 33.9% are within the age bracket of 31 - 40 years. On the same note, 19.7% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 41 - 50 years while the remaining respondents representing 9.7% are within the age bracket of 51 years and above. Table 1 shows that 20 representing 5.7% of the respondents have Ordinary level, 136 representing 38.4% of the respondents have either Ordinary National Diploma or National Certificate on Education as their educational qualification while 153 representing 43.2% of the respondents agreed that they have either Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) or Higher National Diploma (HND). 40 representing 11% of the respondents have either M.Sc./MBA, while 15 representing 4.2% respondents agreed that they have PhD/Others.

Presentation and Analysis of Data Related to Content Marketing and Sales Performance

Table 2 Content Marketing and Sales Performance

Items	SA	A	D	SD	U	Total
Interactive content marketing platform allows real estate firms to engage with real estate customers.	93 (26.3%)	184 (53%)	36 (10.1%)	29 (8.2%)	12 (3.4%)	354
Content marketing platform helps real estate firms to capture customer’s attention very well.	89 (25.1%)	165 (46.6%)	48 (13.6%)	33 (9.3%)	19 (5.4%)	354
Content marketing platform is used to retain customer loyalty for real estate business.	68 (19.2%)	202 (57.1%)	44 (12.5%)	26 (7.3%)	14 (3.9%)	354
Content marketing platform enhance customer’s engagement to real estate business.	89 (25.1%)	165 (46.6%)	48 (13.6%)	33 (9.3%)	19 (5.4%)	354
Content marketing platform provides valuable information to real estate marketers.	202 (57.1%)	68 (19.2%)	44 (12.4%)	26 (7.3%)	14 (4%)	354
Profit after sales has increased due to the use of content marketing by real estate firm.	130 (36.7%)	132 (37.3%)	51 (14.4%)	27 (7.7%)	14 (3.9%)	354

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2 revealed that 53% of the respondents agreed that interactive content marketing platforms allows real estate firms to engage with real estate customers, 26.3% strongly agreed, 10.1% disagreed, 8.2% of the respondents strongly disagreed while 3.4% were undecided. Table 4.1.8 shows that 25.1 % of the respondents strongly agreed that content marketing platform helps real estate firms to capture customers’ attention. 46.6% agreed, 5.4% were undecided, 13.6% disagreed while 9.3% of the respondents strongly disagreed. Table 2 also shows that 19.2% of the respondents strongly agreed that content marketing platform is used to retain customer loyalty for real estate firms. 57.1% agreed, 12.5% disagreed, 7.3% strongly disagreed while 3.9% of the respondents were not sure. The table also revealed that 25.1%of the respondents strongly agreed that content marketing platform enhances customers engagement to real estate, 46.6% agree, 5.4% were undecided, 13.6% disagreed, while 9.3% of the respondents strongly disagreed. Table 2 further revealed that 57.1%of the respondents strongly agreed. 19.2% agreed, 12.4% disagreed, 7.3% strongly disagreed while 4% of the respondents were undecided. Table 2 revealed that 36.7% of respondents strongly agreed that profit after sales has increased due to the use of content marketing by real estate firm. 37.3% agreed, 14.4% disagreed, 7.7% strongly disagreed while 3.9% of respondents were undecided.

Analysis of Regression Result

The regression result is presented in the tables below.

Table 3 Simple Regression Model Summary Result

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.665 ^a	.622	.565	1.875	1.957

a. Predictors: (Constant), Content Marketing

b. Dependent Variable: Sales Performance

Table 4 Simple Regression ANOVA^a Result

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	203.781	1	203.781	51.457	.000 ^b
	Residual	392.078	353	4.257		
	Total	595.859	354			

a. Dependent Variable: Sales Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Content Marketing

Table 5 Simple Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Std. Coefficient	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	β		
1	(Constant)	4.527	1.378		5.100	.006
	Content Marketing	.703	.054	.683	7.137	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Sales Performance

Source: SPSS Computation Output

Table 3 shows the simple regression model summary. A cursory look on the table indicates that regression correlation coefficient is 0.665. This shows a positive relationship between the dependent and independent variables (content marketing and sales performance). The value of coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.662. This entails that content marketing was able to explain 66.2% of the variations on sales performance. Furthermore, about 33.8% (100% - 66.2%) of the variations are caused by other factors not included in the regression model. The adjusted R-square value is 0.565 which is 56.5%, which is about 9.7% (66.2 - 56.5 = 9.7) different from the main R-squared. Also, the standard error of the estimate is 1.875.

Table 4 shows the ANOVA of the regression analysis. The F-statistic value is 51.457 with its corresponding p-value of 0.002. The implication of these results is that the model is fit and significant. The p-value of f-statistics confirmed the fitness of the model. The unstandardized coefficient shows how much the dependent variable varies with an independent variable when other independent variables are held constant. The regression coefficient provides the expected change in the dependent variable (sales performance) for a one-unit increase in the independent variable (content marketing). The unstandardized coefficient value for content marketing is 0.703. This means that for every unit increase in content marketing, the sales performance will increase by 0.703. The standardize coefficient value 0.683. This entails that content marketing was able to contribute 68.3% effects on sales performance of real estate firms. The value of t-statistics is 7.137 and its p-value is 0.002. Since the value of 0.002 is less than 0.05 (5%), the stipulated level of significance used for this study; therefore, content marketing platform has a significant effect on sales performance of real estate firms in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding from this study revealed that content marketing had a significant and positive effect on sales performance of real estate firms in Anambra State. This implies that content marketing enhances the sales performance of real estate companies in Anambra State. The result agrees with the findings of (Chaffey et al., 2019; Keyes, 2016; Pulizzi & Barret, 2019). Content marketing is used to attract and retain customers by consistently creating contents which in return enhance the sales performance of real estate (Halvorson, 2019). The result is also in unity with the finding by (Handley & Chapman, 2019; Gunelius; 2018; Lieb; 2018) that found that content marketing platform has a significant effect on sales performance. To sum it up, the findings from this study confirmed the theories that formed the foundation for this study.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated the effect of content marketing of sales performance of real estate companies in Anambra State. The data sourced from the employees of these companies were subjected to empirical analysis. The study found that content marketing platform has a positive and significant effect on sales performance of real estate firms in Anambra State. Content marketing platform has the $\beta = .685$, t-value of 7.137 and p-value .002 which is statistically significant. The study concludes that content marketing significantly and positively affected the sales performance of real estate firms. The study recommends that real estate firms should invest more on content marketing since it enhanced the sales performance of the real estate firms. Also, content marketing should be design in such a way that it creates a healthy interaction and emotional involvement with the existing and prospective customers.

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